

CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE FORMATION OF BEHAVIOR

Shoira Xudoyqulova

Teacher of the Department of Psychology of Termiz State University

E-mail: soirahudojkulova34@gmail.com

Phone number: (88) 807 31 07

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10359355>

Abstract. *The social environment is also important in the child's environment. Any period requires the formation of moral education and behavioral culture in accordance with the specific tasks of social, economic and cultural development.*

Keywords: *social environment, person, educational process, behavior, education.*

ДЕТИ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО И МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПОВЕДЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В окружении ребенка большое значение имеет и социальная среда. Любой период требует формирования нравственного воспитания и культуры поведения в соответствии с конкретными задачами социального, экономического и культурного развития.*

Ключевые слова: *социальная среда, человек, образовательный процесс, поведение, образование.*

The fate and future of every society and the people living in it are closely related to the education of the youth, who are considered the leading forces of the states. Great work is being done in our country to strengthen the intellectual and creative potential of young people, to increase their involvement in the reforms implemented in our country.

In our country, special importance is attached to the issue of youth education.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, emphasized that youth education is an urgent problem today and deserves special attention: In other words, it is related to worldview. Today, times are changing rapidly. Young people are the ones who feel these changes the most. Let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, he should not forget his identity. Let the call of who we are and the descendants of great people always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to stay true to themselves. How can we achieve this? Education, education and only education." states that. ¹

It is said in the blessed hadith shared by our great muhaddith grandfather Imam Bukhari in the book "Masterpieces of Manners" (Al-Adab al-mufrad) that "No father can give his child a greater legacy than manners."

In the preschool period, moral concepts become more and more strict. The source of moral concepts can be adults involved in their education, as well as their peers. Moral experiences are passed and strengthened mainly in the process of communication, observation, imitation, and at the same time through the praise and criticism of adults, especially mothers. The child always tries to get grades, especially praise. These evaluations and praises are very important in the

¹ Ш.Мирзиёев 5 та муҳим ташаббус. Тошкент, 2019.

development of a child's character of striving for success, as well as in his personal life and career choice.

In kindergarten, children develop new motives for communication. It has personal and business motives. Personal communication motives are related to internal problems that concern the child, and business motives are related to doing one or another job. These motivations are gradually joined by learning motivations related to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities. These motives appear in the place of children's natural curiosity, which starts from early childhood. Self-expression motives are also evident at this age.

The formation of a child's character at the age of junior and middle kindergarten is formed on the basis of children's observation of the character of adults. From these years, important personal characteristics such as will, independence and initiative begin to develop in the child.

At the age of kindergarten, the child begins to learn to communicate and interact with the people around him in various activities. This will benefit him in the future in getting along with people, and being able to establish normal work and personal relationships. In the formation of the personality of children of this age, their opinions about their parents and their evaluations are extremely important.

Kindergarten children's imagination grows mainly in their various play activities. However, it is worth noting that if children of kindergarten age did not have the ability to imagine, their imagination would not be diverse. Kindergarten children's imaginations grow in various activities. Fairy tales are another factor that actively affects the growth of the imagination of children of kindergarten age. When children hear different stories about animals, a certain attitude towards the characters in these stories is formed

Pleasant and unpleasant feelings are very strong and very quick in children of kindergarten age. Kindergarten children's emotions are related to the satisfaction and non-satisfaction of their organic needs. Due to the fact that these needs are not satisfied, the child feels unpleasant (unpleasant), displeasure, and distress.

There is a connection between the sense of duty - the understanding of what is good and what is bad - and their moral imagination in children of senior kindergarten age. Feelings of satisfaction and joy arise when they perform a task ordered by adults, and when they break a rule, they feel sad and depressed.

A child's success in school largely depends on their level of preparation for school. First of all, the child should be physically ready for school. Anatomical and physiological development of 6-year-old children takes place in a unique way.

At this age, the child's body develops rapidly. Its weight increases by 150-200 gm and its height by 0.5 cm per month. 6-year-old children can walk at different speeds, run quickly and easily. They can easily run and jump, skate, ski, swim. Children of this age perform a variety of rhythmic and plastic movements during music lessons, and can perform various exercises accurately, quickly, easily and nimbly.

A child's successful study at school depends not only on his mental and physical fitness, but also on his personal and social-psychological readiness. A child coming to school should be ready to take on a new social status - the position of a student with different obligations and rights and different requirements.

During this period, children's inner personal life begins first in the areas of cognition, and then in the direction of emotional motivation. The development in one direction or another goes through stages from figurative to symbolic. Imagery means children's ability to create different images, change them and move them freely, and symbolism means the ability to work with the sign system (mathematical, linguistic, logical, etc.).

The process of creativity begins at a young age before school. Creativity is mainly manifested in children's constructive games, technical and artistic creations. During this period, the primary development of buds of special abilities begins to be noticed. A synthesis of internal and external actions occurs in cognitive processes. In the process of perceiving something, this synthesis is seen in perceptive actions, in attention, in managing and controlling the plan of internal and external actions and situations, and in memory, in being able to connect the internal and external structure of remembering and remembering the material. And in thinking, it is clearly invisible as the integration of methods of working on practical issues into one general process. Based on this, the human intellect is formed and developed. In the pre-school period, imagination, thinking and speech are generalized.

This is evidence that inner speech is emerging as a factor of thinking in children of this age.

The synthesis of cognitive processes is based on the child's complete mastery of his native language. During this period, the process of speech formation begins to complete. In the process of speech-based education, the child acquires elementary moral norms and rules. These norms and rules govern the child's morals.

Different relationships arise between the child and the people around him, and different motives lie behind these relationships. All this externalizes the child's individuality and turns him into a person who differs from other children not only intellectually, but also morally and motivationally. It is the peak of the personality development of preschool children, and it is the emergence of their personal qualities, abilities, success and failures, and the emergence of a sense of self-awareness.

Educational activity creates an opportunity for a student of junior school age not only to develop cognitive processes at a high level, but also to develop personal characteristics and the child's personality is formed. In addition to leading educational activities, other activities such as games, communication, and work activities have a direct impact on the development of the student's personality.

The motivation of children to enter the competition during the junior school period is considered a psychological need, and this motive gives them strong emotional stress. In fact, these characteristics begin to appear from a different period and are clearly visible in the period of junior school, as well as in the period of adolescence. Children of junior school age evaluate themselves based on the opinions and evaluations given by adults about them. The student's self-esteem depends directly on the teacher's assessment and his success in various activities.

Self-ratings of children of junior school age can be different - high, adequate - suitable or low. Characteristics of children of this age, such as trustworthiness and obedience, provide a good opportunity to educate them as individuals. The period of junior school age can be considered as the period of emergence and strengthening of the main, personal characteristics of the child that

determine success in various activities. In this period, along with the formation of motives for success, qualities such as hard work and independence are developed. The formation of independence in children mainly depends on adults. If the child is overly trusting, obedient, open, then gradually the character of submissiveness and subordination will be strengthened. However, encouraging a child to be independent in time can also lead to the formation of some negative characteristics in him, because he absorbs his life experiences, mainly by imitating someone.

By the end of the junior school period, children, especially girls, begin to pay special attention to their facial structure. In the course of educational activities, students of junior school age develop the ability to coordinate their own behavior and activities, develop the ability to consciously come to an opinion, organize their own activities and the process of learning. It helps to find a solution of interest, the motivation of the student's behavior also changes. In this case, the opinions of friends and the team will be the main motives. Moral feelings and volitional characteristics of a person are formed.

The normative formation of the behavior of children of preschool and junior school age is characterized by the aspects mentioned above. However, the formation of behavior in children does not always happen overnight. Sometimes there are problems with the formation and manifestation of behavior. The most important problems in the formation of behavior in preschool and junior school age affect the formation of their personal qualities and important qualities in their character in the future.

Therefore, in this period, it is important to be very attentive to the issues of individual development, behavior formation, and education of children.

After all, tomorrow's prosperous life is determined by the establishment of a society based on perfect moral principles, the upbringing of a well-rounded child in the family, his becoming physically strong, mentally fresh, intellectually mature, intellectually and morally beautiful.

REFERENCES

1. XUDOYQULOVA, S., & SAYDALIYEVA, M. (2023). The Role of Parental Psychology in the Formation of a Particular Religious Beliefs in A Child. *Eurasian Scientific Herald* 21, 54-58.
2. Khudoykulova Sh. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL METHOD OF DEVELOPING CHILDREN'S BEHAVIOR AND EMOTION. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(12), 107–112.
3. M.Saydaliyeva (2023) Psychodiagnosics of the realitionship between aggressiveness and religion in adolescents (In Muslim and Christian teenagers)
4. Imonova, M. B. (2023). Causes of Suicide Tendency in Adolescents. *Journal of Discoveries in Applied and Natural Science*, 1(1), 62-67.
5. Yadgarova G.T., Avlay O.U. Tarbiyasi qiyin, qaltis guruhga mansub bolalar bilan ishlash (Uslubiy qo'llanma) T.: 2007 y.
6. Игошев К.Е. Опыт социально-психологического анализа личности несовершеннолетних правонарушителей. М.1967, с.67-68.

7. Umarov B.M. O‘zbekistonda voyaga yetmaganlar jinoyatchiligining ijtimoiy-psixologik muammolari. (Monografiya). “Fan” nashriyoti, Toshkent – 2008, 284 b.
8. Juraevna, G. D. (2022). Psychological views on the role of parents in raising children in the family. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(10), 143-147.
9. Juraevna, D. G. (2022). Preparing young boys and girls for family life. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 1513-1517.
10. Juraevna, G. D. (2021). Prevention of divorce by preparing young people for family life. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(12), 398-401.
11. GAFFOROVA, D. (2023). Provoking factors of family breakdown in modern society. *Transnational Journal of Medicine & Health*, 2(10), 3-5.
12. GAFFOROVA, D. (2023). Psychoprophylaxis of monthly conflict generating disagreements in modern society. *Young Scholar’s Academic Journal*, 2(7), 5-7.